

**LIBRARIANS AS POLICY ACTORS: EMPIRICAL INSIGHTS INTO ADVOCACY FOR
ENTREPRENEURIAL SUPPORT IN FEDERAL UNIVERSITY LIBRARIES IN SOUTHWEST
NIGERIA**

Dr Adebola Aderemi OLATOYE

The Nigerian Baptist Theological Seminary,
Ogbomoso, Oyo State.

adebolaadeyemo0108@gmail.com

<https://orcid.org/0009-0006-1555-3355>

+2348038853216

Dr Opeyemi Olufunmilayo BOLOGUN

Osun State University,
Osogbo, Osun State

lamopeyemi2714@gmail.com

<https://orcid.org/0009-0001-1800-9893>

+2347067938113

10.5281/zenodo.18483313

Abstract

The study examined the role of librarians as policy actors in advocating for entrepreneurial support within federal university libraries in Southwest Nigeria. It specifically investigated the extent to which librarians are involved in advocacy for entrepreneurial support services. The study adopted the descriptive survey research design, had a population of 170 librarians across 6 federal university libraries in Southwest Nigeria, and a sample size of 118. Data collected were analysed using statistical tools of tables, charts, frequencies, and percentages. The findings of the study revealed a low extent of direct involvement in advocacy for entrepreneurial support services; the types of entrepreneurial support being entrepreneurship-focused information literacy sessions, and access to business databases and market intelligence tools; findings also revealed that advocacy strategies are largely informal and lack institutional coordination; and the challenges encountered by librarians in policy advocacy include lack of inclusion in university policy and decision-making structure and limited knowledge of policy advocacy and institutional governance; the main enabling factors and best practices that facilitate librarians' successful engagement as policy actors in entrepreneurial development include supportive university leadership, training in advocacy and policy engagement, and formal partnerships with innovation/entrepreneurship centres. The study recommends that federal universities need to align with global trends in entrepreneurship-driven education; and recommended that the policy role of librarians should be institutionalized and supported.

Keywords: *Advocacy, Entrepreneurial support, Entrepreneurship, Librarians, Policy actors*

Introduction

In the evolving landscape of higher education, academic libraries are increasingly expected to transcend their traditional functions as passive custodians of information to become proactive contributors to institutional transformation and national development. One such national priority is the promotion of entrepreneurship, which is seen as a viable strategy to reduce graduate unemployment, foster innovation, and build a resilient economy in Nigeria (National Universities Commission [NUC], 2021; Olowe, et. al, 2023). Consequently, Nigerian universities, particularly federal universities, have been mandated to integrate entrepreneurial education and support services into their core operations (NUC, 2021). While various academic units are responding to this policy shift, the role of university libraries and their professionals in this transformation remains under-examined.

Traditionally, librarians have been confined to supportive academic roles in teaching, learning, and research. However, emerging scholarship repositions librarians as ‘policy actors’ who are influential participants in institutional decision-making processes (Lux, 2024; Okojie, 2020). In this capacity, librarians are expected to advocate for the

alignment of library services with strategic institutional goals, including the promotion of entrepreneurship. Globally, academic librarians have begun to assume more prominent roles in shaping policies that govern scholarly communication, digital literacy, and curriculum development (Arif & Mahmood, 2012; Oladokun, et al. 2025). In the Nigerian context, however, there is a paucity of empirical studies exploring how librarians advocate for or influence entrepreneurial policies within university systems.

As entrepreneurship becomes embedded in university operations, through innovation hubs, business incubation centres, and skills development programmes, libraries are under increasing pressure to reconfigure their services to support this agenda. This includes the provision of entrepreneurship-focused information resources, training in business information literacy, access to market data, and collaborative partnerships with internal stakeholders such as entrepreneurship centres and external actors, including industry experts (Ezeani & Igwesi, 2012; Okike, et. al, 2022). To make meaningful contributions, librarians must move beyond service delivery to become active participants in policy formulation and institutional advocacy. Such

a role demands a combination of leadership, strategic communication, and a nuanced understanding of university governance.

The concept of librarians as policy entrepreneurs, where individuals invest time, resources, and influence to promote significant policy change, has gained traction in library and information science literature (Kingdon, 2014; Uwem & Ajayi, 2023). Within this framework, librarians in Nigerian federal universities have the potential to influence the inclusion and expansion of entrepreneurial support through advocacy, coalition-building, and policy engagement. However, structural barriers such as bureaucratic hierarchies, limited representation in decision-making bodies, and inadequate training in advocacy and policy engagement often impede their influence (Abubakar, 2021).

Statement of the Problem

In response to Nigeria's high unemployment rate and the demand for economic diversification, the Federal Government has mandated the integration of entrepreneurship education and support services into university curricula (NUC, 2021). This shift underscores the need for all academic units, including university libraries, to contribute

meaningfully to the development of entrepreneurial mindsets and infrastructure. University libraries, as knowledge hubs, possess the potential to support entrepreneurship through tailored information services, digital resources, training programs, and collaborative innovation spaces. However, their ability to influence the design and implementation of entrepreneurial policies and initiatives remains underexplored. While librarians have historically played supportive academic roles, there is a growing discourse on their potential to act as policy actors and institutional change agents (Lux, 2024; Uwem & Ajayi, 2023). Despite this evolving role, empirical studies that document how librarians in Nigerian universities advocate for entrepreneurial support, influence institutional decisions, or participate in policy formulation are scarce. Many libraries still function in isolation from the strategic goals of their institutions, with limited involvement in entrepreneurial development programmes.

Moreover, anecdotal evidence suggests that librarians face significant challenges in asserting their roles in policy arenas. These challenges include exclusion from key decision-making bodies, lack of formal

training in policy advocacy, bureaucratic barriers, and institutional cultures that limit librarians' influence beyond traditional roles (Okojie, 2020; Abubakar, 2021). Without deliberate advocacy and strategic engagement, libraries risk being sidelined in university-wide efforts to promote entrepreneurship. The absence of empirical data on how librarians in federal universities in Southwest Nigeria engage in advocacy for entrepreneurial support represents a critical knowledge gap. Understanding the extent, strategies, challenges, and outcomes of such advocacy efforts is essential for repositioning librarians as integral contributors to institutional policy processes. This study therefore seeks to fill this gap by providing empirical insights into how librarians function as policy actors in the context of entrepreneurial support in Nigerian federal university libraries.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to examine the role of librarians as policy actors in advocating for entrepreneurial support within federal university libraries in Southwest Nigeria.

The specific objectives are to:

- i. investigate the extent to which librarians are involved in advocacy for entrepreneurial support services within federal university libraries in Southwest Nigeria.
- ii. identify the types of entrepreneurial support services and initiatives that librarians promote or support.
- iii. examine the strategies and approaches employed by librarians to influence institutional policy or decision-making related to entrepreneurship.
- iv. explore the institutional, professional, and systemic challenges that hinder librarians' effective participation in entrepreneurial policy advocacy.
- v. determine the enabling factors and best practices that facilitate librarians' successful engagement as policy actors in entrepreneurial development.

Review of Literature

Academic libraries have traditionally played a supportive role in university teaching, learning, and research. However, as entrepreneurship becomes a central part of university curricula and strategic missions,

Olowe, et. al (2023) averred that the involvement of librarians in advocating for entrepreneurial services has become increasingly significant. Advocacy, in this context, refers to deliberate actions taken by librarians to influence institutional policy, promote resource allocation, and align library services with emerging university needs. Globally, librarians are beginning to be recognized as institutional influencers capable of driving change beyond traditional library functions (Lux, 2024). In Nigeria, however, librarians' involvement in entrepreneurship-related initiatives remains minimal and under-documented. Abubakar (2021) noted that this lack of involvement is often attributed to structural hierarchies, absence from policy-making committees, and a narrow perception of librarianship within the academic environment.

Entrepreneurial support services in academic libraries can take various forms. Oladokun, et al. (2025) and Okike, et. al (2022) opined that these include the provision of business databases, access to market research tools, information literacy programs tailored to entrepreneurship, intellectual property guidance, and support for innovation hubs. Some academic libraries have gone further to establish makerspaces, collaborative

workspaces, and business development centers within their facilities. In Nigeria, few libraries have made visible strides in this direction. Ezeani & Igwesi (2012) note that while Nigerian academic librarians are aware of the need to support entrepreneurship, most libraries lack structured programs, funding, or trained personnel to provide effective services. Where such services exist, they are often embedded in broader information literacy efforts without clear entrepreneurial targeting.

Effective policy advocacy by librarians requires intentional strategy. Arif and Mahmood (2021) reported that librarians have used approaches such as coalition-building, policy briefing documents, representation on academic boards, strategic partnerships, and alignment with national or institutional goals to influence policy outcomes. Librarians in developed countries often engage with faculty, administrators, and policymakers using evidence-based advocacy and impact metrics to promote new services or roles. In Nigeria, advocacy strategies by librarians are largely informal or reactive. Kingdon (2014) noted that few engage in proactive policy entrepreneurship, where individuals initiate and promote policy change based on expertise and opportunity.

This gap underscores the need for skills training in advocacy, policy communication, and strategic planning among Nigerian academic librarians (Okojie, 2020; Uwem & Ajayi, 2023).

Numerous barriers inhibit librarians' capacity to function as effective policy actors. These include institutional bureaucracy, lack of recognition in university governance structures, inadequate advocacy skills, and limited access to decision-making processes (Abubakar, 2021; Okojie, 2020). Additionally, there exists a cultural perception of librarians as mere support staff, which hinders their involvement in core academic planning. Resource constraints and poorly defined job roles further complicate librarians' ability to advocate for entrepreneurial support. Ezeani and Igwesi (2012) emphasize that without training and institutional backing, librarians are unlikely to engage meaningfully in university policy discussions related to entrepreneurship.

Despite these challenges, several enabling factors have been identified. Oladokun, et al. (2025) argued that these include leadership support from university management, institutional autonomy for library leadership, professional development programs, and

inclusion in academic policy-making bodies. Strong collaboration with entrepreneurship centers and academic departments also empowers librarians to embed entrepreneurial services into university systems. Uwem and Ajayi (2023) argue that a paradigm shift is needed, one that redefines the librarian as a strategic partner in university innovation. Best practices from international contexts show that when librarians are involved early in strategic planning and are equipped with the right tools, their contributions to entrepreneurship and policy development become significant and impactful.

Although the literature provides a growing recognition of the evolving roles of academic librarians as policy actors and supporters of entrepreneurship, most studies focus on Western contexts. Nigerian studies tend to be descriptive rather than analytical or empirical. There is a notable gap in research that critically examines how librarians in federal universities in Nigeria are navigating the intersection of librarianship, advocacy, and entrepreneurship. This study addresses this gap by providing empirical insights into the advocacy roles, strategies, challenges, and enabling conditions of librarians as policy actors in entrepreneurial support. The

findings will serve to broaden the understanding of librarians' impact on institutional policy and contribute to ongoing reforms in academic library services in Nigeria.

Methodology

The study adopted the descriptive survey research design. The population of the study is the 170 librarians in Federal university

libraries in Southwest, Nigeria. The sample size for the study was determined by Krejcie and Morgan (1970) sample size determination. From their Table the sample size is 118. The structured questionnaire is the instrument of data collection for this study. It was subjected to validity by experts in librarianship and reliability using a pilot study from Federal University of Technology, Owerri to test for the reliability. The questionnaire was hosted online and the data were analysed using statistical tools of tables, charts, frequencies, and percentages.

Table 1: Study Population

Federal University in Southwestern Nigeria	Number of Librarians	Sample Size
Federal University of Agriculture, Ogun State	24	16
Federal University of Technology, Ondo State	26	19
Federal University, Ekiti State	12	9
Obafemi Awolowo University, Osun State	28	19
University of Ibadan, Oyo State	60	40
University of Lagos	20	15
Total	170	118

Table 2: Krejcie and Morgan (1970) sample size determination

Population	Sample size	Population	Sample size	Population	Sample size
10	10	15	14	20	19
25	24	30	28	35	32
40	36	45	40	50	44
55	48	60	52	65	56
70	59	75	63	80	66
85	70	90	73	95	76

100	80	110	86	120	92
130	97	140	103	150	108
160	113	170	118	180	123
190	127	200	132	210	136
220	140	230	144	240	148

Presentation of Results and Discussion of Findings

The study surveyed librarians across six federal university libraries in Southwest Nigeria. Of the targeted 118 librarians, a total of 102 valid responses were received, yielding a response rate of 86.4%.

Table 3: Respondents' Demographics

Gender:	Frequency:	Percentage:
Females	58	57%
Males	44	43%
Educational Qualification:	Frequency:	Percentage:
Bachelors	10	10%
Masters	74	73%
Doctorate	18	17%
Work Experience:	Frequency:	Percentage:
0 – 5 years	14	14%
6 – 10 years	27	26%
11 – 15 years	17	17%
16 – 20 years	19	19%
21 years and above	25	24%

The demographic data suggest a mature and professionally qualified respondent base capable of engaging in policy-related discussions.

Figure 1: Extent to librarians' involvement in advocacy for entrepreneurial support services within federal university libraries in Southwest Nigeria

Only 39 (38%) of the respondents reported that they have direct involvement in advocacy efforts related to entrepreneurship. While 48 (47%) of them indicated occasional involvement through committee participation, 15 (15%) of them reported that they do not have any involvement at all. This shows a low level of librarians’ involvement in advocacy for entrepreneurial support services within federal university libraries in Southwest Nigeria. This confirms earlier findings by Okojie (2020) and Abubakar (2021) that Nigerian academic librarians are largely peripheral to institutional decision-making processes. Despite the entrepreneurial thrust in federal universities, libraries are still viewed as supportive rather than strategic units. However, a moderate proportion of librarians are beginning to engage informally or through indirect channels.

Table 4: Types of Entrepreneurial Support Services Provided

Types of Entrepreneurial Support	Yes	No
Entrepreneurship-focused information literacy sessions	63 (62%)	39 (38%)
Access to business databases and market intelligence tools	56 (55%)	46 (45%)
Support for student projects and start-ups through information sourcing	48 (47%)	54 (53%)
Library-hosted seminars and trainings on innovation and business planning	24 (24%)	78 (76%)

The findings reveal the type of entrepreneurial support services provided in federal university libraries in Southwest Nigeria. Top on the chart from respondents’ answers is ‘entrepreneurship-focused information literacy sessions’ with 62%; followed by ‘access to business databases and market intelligence tools’ with 55%; followed by ‘support for student projects and start-ups

through information sourcing, with 47%; and ‘library-hosted seminars and trainings on innovation and business’ with 24%. These services align with Oladokun, et al. (2025) and Okike, et. al (2022), who highlight the evolving functions of academic libraries in supporting knowledge-based economies. However, these initiatives remain fragmented, and only a few libraries have formalized them. Most programmes are ad hoc, often driven by individual librarian initiative rather than institutional integration.

Table 5: Strategies used by Librarians in Policy Advocacy

Policy Advocacy Strategies	Yes	No
Collaboration with entrepreneurship centres	42 (41%)	60 (59%)
Informal lobbying of library committees and faculty boards	36 (35%)	66 (65%)
Writing memos or proposals to management	29 (28%)	73 (72%)
Engaging in cross-functional committees	19 (19%)	83 (81%)

The data reveal that advocacy strategies are largely informal and lack institutional coordination. These findings align with Arif and Mahmood (2012) who argue that without structured advocacy channels, librarians’ influence remains minimal. The findings also support Kingdon’s (2014) theory that policy entrepreneurs must seize ‘policy windows’ to influence change—yet many librarians are not trained to recognize or exploit such opportunities.

Table 6: Challenges faced by Librarians in Policy Advocacy

Challenges in Policy Advocacy	Yes	No
Lack of inclusion in university policy and decision-making structure	69 (68%)	33 (32%)
Limited knowledge of policy advocacy and institutional governance	53 (52%)	49 (48%)
Inadequate funding for entrepreneurship-related resources	49 (48%)	53 (52%)
Perception of librarians as passive support staff	45 (44%)	57 (56%)

According to respondents’ responses, the challenges faced by librarians in policy advocacy are lack of inclusion in university policy and decision-making structure (68%), limited knowledge of policy advocacy and institutional governance (52%), inadequate funding for entrepreneurship-related resources (48%); and perception of librarians as passive support staff (44%). These barriers are consistent with literature by Lux (2024) and Uwem and Ajayi (2023), who found that institutional culture and structural marginalization significantly restrict librarians’ policy roles. Until these systemic constraints are addressed, the ability of librarians to act as effective policy entrepreneurs will remain limited.

Table 7: Enablers and Best Practices Identified

Enablers and Best Practices	Yes	No
Supportive university leadership	34 (33%)	68 (67%)
Training in advocacy and policy engagement	28 (27%)	74 (73%)
Formal partnerships with innovation/entrepreneurship centres	24 (24%)	78 (76%)
Inclusion of the University Librarian in Senate and Council committees	19 (19%)	83 (81%)

The identification of enablers offers hope for transformation. Institutions where librarians are included in strategic planning committees show stronger integration of entrepreneurial library services. This reflects Oladokun, et al. (2025), who stress the importance of leadership, training, and strategic positioning in enabling library innovation.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study examined the evolving role of librarians as policy actors, particularly in the context of advocating for entrepreneurial support in federal university libraries across Southwest Nigeria. The findings reveal that while librarians in these institutions are aware of the importance of supporting entrepreneurial development, their involvement in policy advocacy remains limited, largely informal, and constrained by institutional barriers. Only a few librarians are directly involved in policy-related advocacy, and where engagement does occur, it is often through indirect strategies such as informal lobbying or collaboration with entrepreneurship centres. The entrepreneurial services offered by libraries – such as tailored

information literacy, access to business databases, and support for student innovation – are mostly ad hoc and lack cohesive policy integration. This underscores the need for libraries to move beyond peripheral service delivery and position themselves as strategic partners in institutional planning and policy execution.

Key challenges, such as exclusion from decision-making structures, limited advocacy skills, resource constraints, and cultural perceptions of librarianship, continue to hinder the full participation of librarians as policy actors. However, the study also identified critical enablers, including supportive leadership, professional development opportunities, and structural inclusion in university governance. These

insights suggest a necessary paradigm shift. Academic librarians must be empowered through capacity-building, formal policy inclusion, and strategic collaboration with academic and administrative units. By doing so, they can effectively advocate for and co-create entrepreneurial ecosystems within universities, thereby contributing more meaningfully to national development goals in innovation and economic self-reliance.

In conclusion, if Nigerian federal universities are to align with global trends in entrepreneurship-driven education, the policy role of librarians must be institutionalized and supported. Librarians must not only be seen as custodians of knowledge but also as influential policy actors who help shape the future of higher education and socio-economic development. Thus, the following recommended are proffered for better implementation:

- i. Federal university libraries should institutionalize policy advocacy roles for librarians by ensuring their representation in strategic planning and entrepreneurship development committees. This will formalize their contribution beyond operational support and give them a voice in

policy formulation. The Nigerian Library Association (NLA) and other professional bodies should advocate for policy reforms that acknowledge and empower librarians as key actors in university-level decision-making, particularly in areas related to innovation and entrepreneurship.

- ii. Libraries should develop and integrate entrepreneurship-focused services into their core functions. These may include curated business intelligence resources, innovation labs, and support for students' business planning, aligned with national education goals. Universities should support librarians in creating and sustaining partnerships with entrepreneurship centers, career development units, and external business networks to enhance service relevance and visibility.

- iii. Librarians should be trained in strategic communication and policy advocacy techniques, including writing position papers, leveraging institutional memos, and engaging stakeholders through data-driven proposals. This would enhance their ability to influence policy windows

- effectively. Libraries should create interdisciplinary task forces or working groups that include librarians and entrepreneurship coordinators to co-design and co-implement policy recommendations and service innovations.
- iv. University administrators must address structural and cultural barriers by actively promoting an institutional culture that values the contributions of librarians as intellectual and strategic partners, not just support personnel. There should be dedicated funding for advocacy-related training and resource acquisition, enabling librarians to contribute more robustly to entrepreneurial development and policy dialogue.
- v. Best practices from libraries that have successfully integrated entrepreneurship support, such as inclusive governance, leadership backing, and collaborative programming, should be documented, disseminated, and scaled across other federal universities. Library schools and continuous professional development programmes should embed modules on advocacy, innovation policy, and entrepreneurship support, preparing future librarians to act as change agents in academic settings.

References

- Abubakar, B. M. (2021). Library and information science (LIS) education in Nigeria: Emerging trends, challenges and expectations in the digital age. *Journal of Balkan Libraries Union*, 8(1), 57 – 67. <https://doi.org/10.16918/jblu.932134>
- Arif, M., & Mahmood, K. (2012). The changing role of librarians in the digital world: Adoption of Web 2.0 technologies by Pakistani librarians. *The Electronic Library*, 30(4), 469 – 479. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02640471211252184>

- Ezeani, C. N., & Igwesi, U. (2012). Evaluation of entrepreneurship awareness and skills among LIS students in universities in South East Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, Article 836 <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/836>
- Lux, C. (2024). *The future of advocacy for libraries*. In *Libraries on the Agenda: Lobbying and Advocacy for Library and Information Professionals* (pp. 276 – 282). De Gruyter Saur. <https://doi.org/10.1515/978311076087-019>
- Oladokun, B. D., Enakrire, R. T., Ajani, Y. A., & Azaki, J. Y. (2025). Leadership styles and adoption of 5IR in libraries of higher education. *Library Leadership & Management*, 38(3), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.5860/llm.v38i3.7619>
- Kingdon, J. W. (2014). *Agendas, alternatives, and public policies* (Updated 2nd ed.). Pearson.
- National Universities Commission. (2021). *Guidelines for the implementation of entrepreneurship studies in Nigerian universities*. Abuja: NUC.
- Okike, B. I., Adebayo, M., & Ogbonna, A. U. (2022). The role of university libraries in supporting entrepreneurship education in Nigeria. *Nigerian Libraries*, 55(1), 80–93.
- Okojie, V. (2020). Academic librarians and policy advocacy: Emerging roles in Nigerian universities. *Library and Information Science Digest*, 5(1), 15–27.
- Olowe, T. O., Ajayi, R. O., & Olorunsola, R. (2023). Bridging the gap: Academic libraries and entrepreneurship education in Nigerian universities. *Journal of Librarianship and Information Science in Africa*, 10(2), 51–67.
- Uwem, S. A., & Ajayi, T. F. (2023). Academic librarians as policy entrepreneurs: A study of selected Nigerian federal universities. *International Journal of Library and Information Science Studies*, 9(2), 25–42.